

THE SOCIAL AND CULTURAL IMPORTANCE OF THE LATIN LANGUAGE AND ITS PRESENT AND HISTORICAL LANDSCAPE

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the social and cultural importance of the Latin language. It discusses the modern and historical world of the Latin language, its linguocultural and sociolinguistic significance, its general cultural place, origin and development trends. It provides information about the linguistic and cultural importance of the Latin language in the development of other languages, its interlinguistic relations, and its place and role today.

In today's developing era, it is a clear fact that language is mutually important and occupies an important place in every field. The Latin language (self-called lingua latina), or Latin, is the language of the Latin-Faliscan subgroup of the Italic languages of the Indo-European language family. Latin is one of the most ancient written Indo-European languages.

The historical role of the Latin language as the international language of science and fiction significantly distinguishes it from the numerous artificial languages proposed for international communication - both from those that received at least limited distribution, and from the incomparably larger part of them, which remained stillborn projects. Being the official language of the multi-tribal Roman Empire, which occupied by the 3rd century. AD a vast territory around the Mediterranean Sea, Latin turned out to be the only cultural language in its western part. It retained this significance even after the fall of the Western Roman Empire in the 5th century under the pressure of barbarian tribes.

Until the XII - XIII centuries. Latin remained the only literary language, an instrument of artistic creativity and scientific thought, but above all, the language of the Catholic religion, which formed the basis of medieval ideology.

In the oral speech of numerous Romanized tribes, the Latin language changed so much that already in the 3rd - 4th centuries. it has evolved into a number of local dialects. Subsequently, these dialects laid the foundation for modern Romance languages. The purpose of this work is to reveal the meaning of the Latin language in the modern world.

During the work, the following tasks were solved:

- - determine the history of the development of the Latin language;
- - consider the general cultural significance of the Latin language in the modern world.

Results and discussion

Currently, the Latin alphabet is familiar to almost all people on Earth, since it is studied by all schoolchildren either in mathematics lessons or in foreign language lessons (not

to mention the fact that for many languages the Latin alphabet is native), therefore it is the “alphabet of international communication” . Most artificial languages are based on the Latin alphabet, in particular Esperanto, Interlingua, Ido and others. For all languages with a non-Latin script, there are also systems for writing in Latin - even if a foreigner does not know the correct reading, it is much easier for him to deal with familiar Latin letters than with “Chinese letters”. In a number of countries, the Latin auxiliary letter is standardized and children study it at school (in Japan, China).

Writing in Latin in a number of cases is dictated by technical difficulties: international telegrams were always written in Latin; in email and on web forums you can also often find the Russian language written in Latin letters due to the lack of support for the Cyrillic alphabet or due to mismatched encodings.

On the other hand, in texts in a non-Latin alphabet, foreign names are often left in Latin due to the lack of a generally accepted and easily recognizable spelling in their system. For example, sometimes in Russian text Japanese names are written in Latin, although for the Japanese language there are generally accepted rules for transliteration into the Cyrillic alphabet.

The famous Danish linguist Otto Jespersen was also a supporter of global Latinization. At present, the importance of the Latin language, naturally, is not so great, nevertheless, it plays a very important role in the system of humanities education. Latin Romance language science. The Latin language, as already mentioned, is necessary when studying modern Romance languages, since the history of these languages, many phonetic and grammatical phenomena, and features of vocabulary can only be understood on the basis of knowledge of Latin. The above, although to a lesser extent, also applies to those who study Germanic languages (English, German), on whose grammatical and, especially, lexical system the Latin language also had a great influence. The Latin language will also provide undoubted help to the Russian philologist, for only it allows one to explain the difference in the meaning and spelling of words such as, for example, “company” and “campaign”; spelling of words with so-called “unverifiable” vowels, such as “pessimist”, “optimist”; the presence of one root, but in three variants in the words “fact”, “defect”, “deficiency”, etc.

The Latin language is certainly necessary for a historian, and not only for a specialist in ancient history, which goes without saying, but also for a student of the Middle Ages, all of whose documents are written in Latin.

A lawyer cannot do without studying the Latin language, since Roman law formed the basis of modern Western European law and, through Byzantine law, influenced the most ancient sources of Russian law (treaties between Russians and Greeks, Russian Truth).

There is no doubt about the need to study Latin in medical and veterinary institutes, in biological and natural sciences faculties of universities.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the Latin language, along with ancient Greek, still serves as a source for the formation of international socio-political and scientific terminology.

Thus, we define the following conditions for the need to study Latin:

- 1. Most European languages are based on Latin, and studying it allows you to quickly and easily understand the principles of composing words in these languages. In addition, some words are spelled the same or very close to Latin, despite different pronunciation.

Therefore, you can learn how to write them much faster. Studying the Latin language develops grammatical thinking, teaches you to see the structure of the language, which contributes to the assimilation of the grammar of the Russian language and modern foreign languages.

•2. The terminology of all scientific disciplines is of Greek-Latin origin. This is especially important for biology, medicine, law, mathematics, physics, and chemistry. Moreover, this applies not only to higher specialized education, but also to the school curriculum. It is very difficult to learn terms if it is not clear what words they are derived from.

•3. Taxonomy in anatomy, botany, zoology is based exclusively on the Latin language, even in those rare cases when the entry is made in Cyrillic letters.

•4. In modern active spoken Russian there are several tens of thousands of words that came from the Latin language without changes, or containing Latin bases: astronomy, library, quarter, melody, paragraph, physics and many others.

•5. Studying Latin catchphrases makes it much easier to isolate and memorize word-forming units and increases the general level of culture.

•6. One way or another, all European alphabets are based on the Latin alphabet.

•7. The Latin alphabet is the phonetic basis for the international transcription of all foreign languages.

•8. Almost all variables in all fields of knowledge are usually denoted by Latin and, less often, Greek letters.

•9. Studying the Latin language provides the foundation for a humanitarian education, which opens access to a more adequate perception and understanding of philosophy, literature, painting and other sciences.

Thus, Latin is the language of a rich, more than two thousand-year-old literary tradition, one of the most important languages of science. Along with Hebrew and ancient Greek, Latin has become the most valuable linguistic and cultural heritage of humanity.

The role of the Latin language in world culture is difficult to overestimate. It was Latin that gave birth to many European languages and entered their vocabulary. Outstanding works of ancient Roman literature were written in Latin, and it was this language that became the international language of science. The Latin language (Latin) is one of the Indo-European languages of the Italic group, in which - from about the 6th century. BC. to 6th century AD - said the ancient Romans and which was the official language of the Roman Empire. Until the beginning of modern times, Latin was considered one of the main written languages of Western European science, culture and social life. It is also the official language of the Vatican and the Roman Catholic Church (until the mid-20th century, it was also used in Catholic worship).

Conclusion

This is the language of a rich, more than two thousand-year-old literary tradition, one of the most important languages of universal human culture, which continues to be actively used in some fields of knowledge (medicine, biology, general scientific terminology of the natural sciences and humanities).

Currently, the Latin alphabet is familiar to almost all people on Earth, since it is studied by all schoolchildren either in mathematics lessons or in foreign language lessons (not to mention the fact that for many languages the Latin alphabet is native), therefore it is the

“alphabet of international communication” . Most artificial languages are based on the Latin alphabet, in particular Esperanto, Interlingua, Ido and others.

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